

Role of C-Reactive Protein and Procalcitonin in Predicting Anastomotic Leak in Bowel Surgery.

Chekuri Dharaneesh¹, Subrat Kumar Sahu², M S N Chaturvedhi³, Vedavyas Mohapatra⁴, Amaresh Mishra⁵, Sanjukta Mishra⁶

¹Post Graduate Trainee, Department of General Surgery, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

²Professor, Department of General Surgery, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

³Post Graduate Trainee, Department of General Surgery, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

⁴Associate Professor & Head, Department of G I Surgery, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

⁵Professor & Head, Department of General Surgery, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

⁶Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 25-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Subrata Kumar Sahu

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Objectives: The present study was to investigate and correlated the role of C-reactive protein (CRP) and procalcitonin (PCT) in predicting anastomotic leaks in bowel surgery.

Methods: The study was used to capture a wide variety of cases having intestinal surgery by recruiting all eligible patients. This would enable a thorough analysis of the impact of procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) in predicting anastomotic leaks. This systematic enrolment process contributed to the reliability and validity of the study findings. Access to the clinical and analytical resources required for a thorough evaluation of patients undergoing colon surgery was made possible by this cooperative environment. Procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) serum levels were routinely assessed prior to surgery as well as on days 1, 4, and 7.

Results: Elevated DAY7 values in participants with anastomotic leakage may signify prolonged inflammation and infection, affecting the levels of CRP and procalcitonin. As biomarkers of inflammation and infection, CRP and procalcitonin levels may be substantially elevated in response to the presence of leakage, aiding in the prediction and early detection of anastomotic complications.

Conclusions: Anastomotic leak pose serious threats to the life of the patient and put extra financial burden thereof. However apart from analysing factors for prevention of anastomotic leak, early suspicion of it also carries a lot of importance. Because early intervention specifically within first 10 days can very well minimise the detrimental impact of this ghastly postoperative condition. However, because clinical symptoms are often ambiguous and there are not many trustworthy biomarkers for early identification, leak diagnosis difficult. Hence there is always a room for use of biomarkers for early detection of anastomotic leak. Ultimately, the integration of biomarker monitoring into routine postoperative care protocols has the potential to revolutionize patient care and improve outcomes following bowel surgery.

Key words: C-Reactive Protein, Procalcitonin, Anastomotic Leak, Bowel Surgery.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Anastomotic leaks are among the most serious complications following bowel surgery, presenting significant challenges for patients and healthcare providers alike. These leaks occur when the integrity of the surgical connection (anastomosis) between two segments of the bowel is compromised, resulting in the leakage of

gastrointestinal contents into the peritoneal cavity [1].

The diagnosis of anastomotic leaks poses significant challenges in clinical practice, primarily due to the nonspecific nature of clinical signs and symptoms and the limitations of existing diagnostic modalities. The identification of anastomotic leaks

remains elusive despite developments in surgical procedures and perioperative care. Therefore, healthcare personnel must have a thorough grasp of the current diagnostic hurdles that they encounter [2].

Biomarkers are essential for the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of many illnesses, including post-bowel surgery anastomotic leaks. In the context of anastomotic leaks, biomarkers serve as objective indicators of the inflammatory response, tissue injury, and infectious burden, offering valuable insights into the presence, severity, and progression of postoperative complications. Comprehending the function of biomarkers in the identification and handling of anastomotic leaks necessitates a grasp of their modes of operation, practical significance, and possible constraints.

C-reactive protein (CRP) is an acute-phase reactant that the liver produces in reaction to inflammation and tissue damage, and it is one of the main biomarkers utilized in the evaluation of anastomotic leakage. In the postoperative phase, elevated CRP levels may be a sign of surgical problems such as leaks, wound infections, or abscesses, as well as persistent systemic inflammation. Serial monitoring of CRP levels allows for trend analysis and early detection of complications, enabling timely intervention to mitigate morbidity and mortality [3]. Additionally, CRP measurements may help guide the duration and intensity of antibiotic therapy, optimize wound management strategies, and inform clinical decision-making in the postoperative setting.

Procalcitonin (PCT) is another biomarker that has garnered considerable interest in the assessment of anastomotic leaks. PCT is a precursor of calcitonin that is released in response to bacterial infection and systemic inflammation. A bacterial infection or sepsis may be indicated by elevated PCT levels during the postoperative phase, which would need additional testing to look for leak development or other infectious problems [4]. PCT measurements offer rapid turnaround time and may help differentiate infectious from non-infectious causes of postoperative fever, facilitating appropriate antimicrobial therapy and preventing the unnecessary use of antibiotics [5].

The capacity of CRP and PCT to represent the degree of tissue damage, systemic inflammatory response, and infectious burden after intestinal surgery is one of the mechanisms of action that underpins their prognostic utility in diagnosing anastomotic leaks. The integrity of the gastrointestinal barrier is compromised by anastomotic leaks, which cause luminal contents to leak into the peritoneal cavity and set off an inflammatory cascade marked by the release of

proinflammatory cytokines, immune cell activation, and the recruitment of inflammatory mediators to the site of injury. Increased levels of CRP and PCT, which act as indicators of inflammation, tissue damage, and infection, are indicative of this systemic inflammatory response [6].

CRP and PCT offer advantages in leak prediction by quantifying the systemic inflammatory response and tissue damage associated with leaks. Increased levels could be a sign of persistent infection or inflammation, raising the possibility of leaks or other issues. Serial monitoring enables trend analysis and early leak detection, facilitating timely intervention.

Aims & Objectives:

1. To investigate the role of C-reactive protein (CRP) and procalcitonin (PCT) in predicting anastomotic leaks in bowel surgery.
2. To evaluate PCT and CRP levels in patients undergoing intestinal surgery at different postoperative intervals.
3. To establish a correlation between the incidence of anastomotic leaks following surgery and CRP and PCT levels.
4. To ascertain the degree to which PCT and CRP are diagnostically accurate in identifying patients who are at high risk of anastomotic leakage.
5. To assess PCT and CRP's potential to function as early warning signs of anastomotic leak development, allowing for prompt intervention.

Methodology

Study Population: Patients undergoing bowel anastomosis surgery between June 2022 and September 2024 who were sequentially admitted to the General Surgery Department at KIMS and PBM Hospital in Bhubaneswar made up the study population. This inclusive approach ensured the representation of a diverse patient cohort undergoing bowel surgery within the specified timeframe. By enrolling patients undergoing both small and large bowel anastomosis.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Every patient having a big or small bowel anastomosis in the departments specified above.
- Patients aged 18 years or older.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Obvious sources of infection.
- Autoimmune diseases.
- Cirrhosis of the liver.
- Pancreatitis.
- Heart conditions such as stroke or coronary heart disease.

- Chronic kidney disease, such as CKD.
- Patients with severe trauma.
- Patients on steroids or immune suppressant drugs.

Sample Size Calculation: Based on an anticipated specificity of 72% for PCT and an anticipated prevalence of 9.4% for anastomotic leakage (AL), 84 participants were included in the sample. PCT has a 100% sensitivity and a 72% specificity. 10% relative precision and a 95% confidence interval were employed in the sample size computation.

Sampling Procedure: All eligible patients undergoing bowel anastomotic surgery were systematically enrolled in the study following stringent inclusion and exclusion criteria. This approach ensured the comprehensive inclusion of patients meeting the predefined criteria, minimizing selection bias and enhancing the representativeness of the study population. The study planned to capture a wide variety of cases having intestinal surgery by recruiting all eligible patients. This would enable a thorough analysis of the impact of procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) in predicting anastomotic leaks. This systematic enrolment process contributed to the reliability and validity of the study findings.

Study Setting: Supported by the Department of Biochemistry, the study was carried out in the General Surgery Department at KIMS and PBM Hospital, Bhubaneswar. Access to the clinical and analytical resources required for a thorough evaluation of patients undergoing colon surgery was made possible by this cooperative environment. Procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) serum levels were routinely assessed prior to surgery as well as on days 1, 4, and 7.

Data Collection: A pretested case record proforma was used to carefully collect data, guaranteeing accuracy and consistency in patient recordkeeping. Appropriate techniques were used to do statistical analysis of the gathered data in order to obtain significant insights on the predictive usefulness of PCT and CRP in detecting anastomotic leakage. The rigor and validity of the study findings were enhanced by the systematic method of data collecting in a fully furnished clinical setting.

Method of Follow-Up: For the method of follow-up, patients were instructed to return to the hospital every three weeks post-discharge for essential investigations and interventions, ensuring comprehensive monitoring of their postoperative progress.

Elimination of Bias: Selection bias was mitigated by including all eligible patients in the trial, which helped to remove bias. By carefully measuring and double-checking study variables to guarantee accuracy and dependability, information bias was

reduced. This methodology preserved the authenticity of the gathered data, augmenting the credibility of the research outcomes. The study upheld a high quality of scientific rigor by following strict methods for bias elimination and follow-up, which strengthened the validity of its findings about the predictive relevance of PCT and CRP in diagnosing anastomotic leaks after intestinal surgery.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed by using IBM SPSS version 20.0 software. Chi-square tests, t-tests, and ANOVA test were applied. P value was taken less than or equal to 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$) for significant differences.

Results

The “age distribution of participants involved in the study, providing a comprehensive insight into the demographic composition of the research sample. The table consists of four age categories: 15-35 years, 36-55 years, 56-75 years, and 76-95 years. Each category is accompanied by corresponding values denoting the frequency, percentage, valid percentage, and cumulative percentage of participants within that age range. The Frequency column indicates the number of participants falling into each age group. For instance, there were 23 participants aged 15-35 years, 32 participants aged 36-55 years, 25 participants aged 56-75 years, and 4 participants aged 76-95 years.

The Percent column provides the proportion of participants within each age category relative to the total sample size. It shows that the largest proportion of participants fell within the 36- 55 years age range (38.1%), followed by the 56-75 years age range (29.8%), 15-35 years age range (27.4%), and finally the 76-95 years age range (4.8%).

Among the 84 participants included in the study, 49 were male and 35 were female. This distribution indicates that males represented approximately 58.3% of the study population, while females accounted for about 41.7%. Understanding the gender distribution is crucial for analyzing potential differences or similarities in the predictive abilities of CRP and PCT between male and female participants.

Among the 84 participants enrolled in the study, 31 individuals had no documented comorbidities, constituting approximately 36.9% of the sample. Conversely, 53 participants had existing comorbidities, representing about 63.1% of the cohort. This distribution underscores the prevalence of comorbidities within the study population, a factor that could significantly influence the prognosis and outcomes following bowel surgery.

Table 1: Detailed breakdown of the site of anastomosis among the participants in the study

Site of Anastomosis	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Colo-Colic	20	23.8	23.8
Colo-Rectal	3	3.6	3.6
Esophago-Jejunal and Jejuno- Jejunal	1	1.2	1.2
Gastro-Jejunal and Jejuno-Jejunal	1	1.2	1.2
ILEO-CAECAL And ILEO-CEACEL	2	2.4	2.4
Ileo-Colic	18	21.4	21.4
Ileo-Ileal	16	19.0	19.0
Jejuno-Ileal	4	4.8	4.8
Jejuno-Jejunal	19	22.6	22.6
Total	84	100.0	100.0

The most common type of anastomosis observed was Ileo-colonic, with 18 occurrences, constituting 21.4% of the total sample. Similarly, Colo-colic anastomoses were the second most prevalent, with 20 occurrences, representing 23.8% of the

participants. Some less common types of anastomoses were also identified, such as Esophago-jejunal and Jejuno- jejunal, Gastro-jejunal and Jejuno-jejunal, and Ileo-caecal, each with only one occurrence.

Table 2: Distribution of the types of anastomoses performed among the participants in the study

Type of Anastomosis	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
End To End	52	61.9	61.9
End To End Anastomosis	4	4.8	4.8
End To End and Side To Side	1	1.2	1.2
Side To Side	27	32.1	32.1
Total	84	100.0	100.0

The most common type of anastomosis observed was End to End, with 52 occurrences, constituting 61.9% of the total sample. This indicates that a substantial portion of the participants underwent this particular surgical technique. Side to Side anastomoses were the second most prevalent, with

27 occurrences, representing 32.1% of the participants. Other less common types of anastomoses, such as End to End Anastomosis and End to End and Side to Side, were also identified, though they occurred at lower frequencies.

Table 3: Distribution of suture materials used in the study for performing bowel surgery anastomoses

Suture Material	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Proline 3-0	68	81.0	81.0
Vicryl 3-0	16	19.0	19.0
Total	84	100.0	100.0

The predominant suture material utilized was PROLINE 3-0, with 68 occurrences, accounting for 81.0% of the total sample. This indicates that a significant majority of participants underwent bowel surgery with this particular suture material.

In contrast, VICRYL 3-0 suture material was less commonly used, with 16 occurrences, representing 19.0% of the participants.

Table 4: Detection of anastomotic leakage following bowel surgery

Detection of Leakage and Day	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
No Anastomotic Leak	74	88.1	88.1
Anastomotic Leak Present	10	11.9	11.9
Total	84	100.0	100.0

The majority of participants, 74 individuals (88.1% of the total sample), did not experience anastomotic leakage postoperatively. This highlights the overall success rate of the surgical procedures and postoperative management protocols in preventing complications such as leaks.

However, 10 participants (11.9% of the total sample) did experience anastomotic leakage, indicating that this complication occurred in a minority of cases. Detecting and addressing leaks promptly is essential for minimizing associated morbidity and mortality.

Figure 1: Overview of patient outcomes following bowel surgery

The majority of patients, 77 individuals (91.7% of the total sample), experienced a favorable outcome, as indicated by the category Now patient is taking oral diet normally. This suggests successful recovery and the absence of significant complications requiring prolonged dietary restrictions.

Table 5: Cross-tabulation of the detection of anastomotic leakage and the associated agegroups

Variable	15 - 35 Years	36 - 55 Years	56 - 75 Years
No AnastomoticLeak	22	29	20
Anastomotic Leak Present	1	3	5
Total	23	32	25

Among participants aged 15 - 35 years, 22 individuals experienced no anastomotic leak, while 1 individual had anastomotic leakage present. Similarly, among participants aged 36 - 55 years, 29 individuals had no anastomotic leak, and 3 individuals had anastomotic leakage present.

Table 6: Cross-tabulation of the detection of anastomotic leakage and the associated genders

Variable	Male	Female	Total
No Anastomotic Leak	40	34	74
Anastomotic Leak Present	9	1	10
Total	49	35	84

Among male participants, 40 individuals experienced no anastomotic leak, while 9 individuals had anastomotic leakage present. Among female participants, 34 individuals experienced no anastomotic leak, and 1 individual had anastomotic leakage present.

Table 7: Comprehensive information on the descriptive statistics and the results of independent samples t-tests for CRP DAY1 and PROCALCITONIN DAY1

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
CRP Day 1				1.140	82	0.257	30.015	26.32324	
No Anastomotic Leak	7	155.14	79.527	1.320	12.8	0.210	30.015	22.740	-
Anastomotic Leak Present	4	134	402		54		338	834	19.169
									840 to 79.200
									516
Anastomotic Leak Present	1	125.12	65.702	2.286	50.1	0.026	5.7524	2.5160	0.69912
	0	600	195		29		14	37	8 to
									10.805699
Procalcitonin Day 1				1.039	82	0.302	5.7524	5.5342	
							14	44	

Procalcitonin Day1: The t-test for equality of means (assuming equal variances) yields a t-value of 1.039 with 82 degrees of freedom and a two-tailed significance level of .302, indicating no significant difference in mean procalcitonin levels between the groups.

The t-test for equality of means (not assuming equal variances) yields a t-value of 2.286 with 50.129 degrees of freedom and a two-tailed significance level of .026, indicating a significant difference in mean procalcitonin levels between the groups.

Figure 2: Results of independent samples t-tests for the variable DAY4

Overall, the significant differences in DAY4 values between participants with and without anastomotic leakage underscore the importance of monitoring postoperative patients for early signs of complications. CRP and procalcitonin levels may

serve as valuable indicators in this regard, potentially enhancing the study's predictive capabilities in identifying patients at risk of anastomotic leak following bowel surgery.

Figure 3: Results of independent samples t-tests for the variable DAY7.

The significant differences in DAY7 values between participants with and without anastomotic leakage underscore the importance of monitoring postoperative patients for early signs of complications. CRP and procalcitonin levels may serve as valuable indicators in this context, potentially enhancing the study's predictive capabilities in identifying patients at risk of anastomotic leak following bowel surgery.

Table 8: provides detailed statistics and the results of independent samples t-tests for two variables, age and sex, categorized by the detection of anastomotic leakage (no anastomotic leak and anastomotic leak present).

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error of Mean	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of Difference
Age										
No Anastomotic Leak	74	2.0541	0.85835	0.09978	-1.891	82	0.062	-0.54595	0.28864	-0.12014 to 0.02825
Anastomotic Leak Present	10	2.6000	0.84327	0.26667						
Sex										
No Anastomotic Leak	74	1.4595	0.50176	0.05833	2.200	82	0.031	0.35946	0.16336	0.03448 to 0.68444
Anastomotic Leak Present	10	1.1000	0.31623	0.10000						

The t-test for equality of means, both assuming and not assuming equal variances, shows that the p-values (.444 and .369, respectively) are greater than the typical alpha level of .05. This suggests that there is no significant difference in mean suture material values between the groups, regardless of whether equal variances are assumed or not. The

findings suggest that the type of suture material used in bowel surgery may not significantly impact the predictive abilities of CRP and procalcitonin in identifying anastomotic leaks. This implies that other factors may have a more substantial influence on the accuracy of CRP and procalcitonin as predictive biomarkers in this context.

Diagonal segments are produced by ties.

Figure 4: Roc Analysis Graph 2 : For Crp and Procalcitonin InAnastomosis Leak On Day 1, Day 4 And Day 7

The Area Under the Curve (AUC) serves as a measure of how effectively each test result variable can differentiate between positive and negative outcomes. Specifically, the AUC values for the various test result variables are as follows: CRP DAY1 with an AUC of 0.601, PROCALCITONIN DAY1 with an AUC of 0.571, DAY4 with an AUC of 0.126, another instance of DAY4 with an AUC of 0.130, crp_DAY7 with an AUC of 0.024, and DAY7 with an AUC of 0.019. These values provide insights into the discriminatory power of each variable, aiding in the assessment of their effectiveness in identifying the desired outcomes.

The findings suggest that the ability to detect anastomosis leaks notably improves on Day 4 and Day 7 when both C-reactive protein (CRP) and procalcitonin (PROCALCITONIN) are employed as diagnostic markers.

The Area Under the Curve (AUC) values obtained for CRP on Day 4 and Day 7 were 0.126 and 0.024, respectively. Similarly, the AUC values for PROCALCITONIN on these days were 0.130 and 0.019, respectively.

Despite the low AUC values for both markers individually, when combined, they exhibit enhanced discriminatory power in identifying anastomosis leaks on Day 4 and Day 7. This synergy suggests that the simultaneous assessment of CRP and PROCALCITONIN levels improves diagnostic accuracy, offering a more reliable means of detecting anastomosis leaks during these critical postoperative periods.

Discussions

In our study as per sample size calculation we have 84 number of cases accrued in a span of 2yrs. The patients were mostly of age group between 15 – 75yrs and males slightly dominant. The number of cases 36.9% had no co-morbidities and 63.1% has co-morbidities.

Among the site of anastomosis 23.8% were colocolic, 21.4% were ileocolic, 19% were ileoileal and 22.6% were jejuno-jenunal so rest 13.2% cases comprise other anastomosis. Most of the anastomosis are end to end anastomosis. In fact, where there is gross luminal disparity we have gone for side to side or end to side anastomosis and in other cases end to end anastomosis. All anastomosis were done in two layer with 3-0 or 2-0 PDS for inner layer and vicryl/ silk for outer layer. For end to end anastomosis interrupted sutures and for side to side continuous sutures are used in consideration with vascularity.

The patients were followed up post-operatively with close monitoring for sepsis; gut content in drain or main wound, aspiration of gut content in abdominal collection, as well as CRP,

Procalcitonin on DAY 1, 4 and 7. Around 10% patients suffered from anastomosis leak and were salvaged by re-laparotomy. 3 patients died due to anastomotic leak.

Day-1 CRP and Procalcitonin is not much different between two groups (with anastomotic leak Vs without anastomotic leak). However, day-4 and day-7 values are significantly different between two groups. More so day-7 values are statistically significant for those with anastomotic leak. The findings suggest that the ability to detect anastomotic leaks improve on day-4 and day-7. When both the markers are used together. No of cases where CRP and procalcitonin level is significant but were detected with leak after 4th day or 7th day in 5 patients.

Evaluating the kinetics of CRP and PCT and their efficacy in detecting anastomotic leaks, the first study, "C-reactive protein and procalcitonin for the early detection of anastomotic leakage after elective colorectal surgery, prospectively analyzed data from 100 patients undergoing elective colorectal surgery. Those with anastomotic leaks had considerably higher levels of PCT and CRP than those without such leaks, according to the research. Significantly, CRP showed better accuracy than PCT in detecting leaks, especially on postoperative day 4, with an area under the receiver-operating characteristics (ROC) curve of 0.869 as opposed to 0.750. Results like this imply that CRP might be a trustworthy biomarker for leak detection early on, allowing for prompt action and better patient outcomes [7].

Some of the previous studies [8,9] together provide important information about the clinical utility of PCT and CRP in bowel surgery, especially in terms of anticipating anastomotic leak. Procalcitonin may provide better diagnostic precision, especially for significant leaks, even though CRP may be a trustworthy biomarker for early leak diagnosis, especially on postoperative day 4. To validate these results in bigger cohorts and investigate the best cutoff values and clinical criteria for biomarker interpretation, more investigation is necessary. In the end, routine postoperative care procedures that incorporate PCT and CRP monitoring may improve patient outcomes and optimize clinical management in the setting of colon surgery.

The age distribution table provides valuable insights into the demographic composition of the study cohort, elucidating the age ranges represented among the participants. By delineating participants into distinct age categories, ranging from 15 to 95 years, the table offers a comprehensive overview of the age demographics, facilitating a nuanced analysis of potential age-related differences in surgical outcomes and biomarker profiles.

The present study provides information on the

incidence of anastomotic leaking after colon surgery and illustrates how successful surgical techniques are in avoiding this consequence. The table offers vital information on the frequency and time of leakage detection by classifying participants according to the presence or absence of anastomotic leaks. This information helps to optimize postoperative monitoring techniques and therapies.

It provides a comprehensive overview of patient outcomes following bowel surgery, ranging from successful recovery to adverse events such as mortality and complications. Analysing these outcomes offers valuable insights into the spectrum of postoperative morbidity and mortality, guiding efforts to optimize surgical techniques and postoperative care protocols to enhance patient safety and outcomes.

The biomarker analysis provides comprehensive information about the possible use of procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) as predictive biomarkers for anastomotic leakage after bowel surgery. In-depth data and the outcomes of independent samples t-tests comparing CRP and PCT levels between patients with and without anastomotic leak at various postoperative time points (days 1, 4, and 7).

The two groups' CRP and PCT levels differ, as shown by the descriptive statistics. Yet, whether equal variances were assumed or not, the independent samples t-tests show no discernible difference in the mean CRP levels across the groups. Similarly, when identical variances were assumed, no discernible variation in mean PCT levels was discovered. On the other hand, a substantial variation in the groups' mean PCT levels was noted when equal variances were not assumed.

The groups' CRP and PCT levels differ noticeably, according to the descriptive statistics. Day 4 post-surgery levels of CRP and PCT are considerably influenced by the existence of anastomotic leakage, according to the independent samples t-tests, which show a significant difference in these biomarker levels between the groups.

The groups' CRP and PCT levels varied significantly, according to the descriptive statistics. Anastomotic leaking appears to have a considerable impact on the levels of these biomarkers on day 7 post-surgery, as indicated by the significant differences in mean CRP and PCT levels between the groups as determined by the independent samples t-tests.

Overall, the biomarker analysis demonstrates that CRP and PCT levels may serve as potential indicators for predicting anastomotic leakage following bowel surgery. While no significant differences were observed on day 1, significant

differences were detected on days 4 and 7 post-surgery, indicating the potential utility of these biomarkers in predicting and monitoring postoperative complications.

These results imply that monitoring CRP and PCT levels, especially on days 4 and 7 after surgery, may help in the early detection and treatment of anastomotic leakage. These findings have significant implications for clinical practice. Furthermore, the notable variations in biomarker levels between patients with and without anastomotic leakage highlight how crucial it is to take these variables into account when making decisions about postoperative treatment.

The study "Procalcitonin, as an early biomarker of colorectal anastomotic leak, facilitates enhanced recovery after surgery assessed the predictive usefulness of PCT levels in identifying anastomotic leak by prospectively analyzing 99 patients undergoing colorectal surgery. In comparison to CRP and white blood cell count (WBC), the results showed that lower PCT levels had a substantial negative predictive value for anastomotic leak on the third and fifth postoperative days. Crucially, the best diagnostic performance was obtained by combining the measures of PCT and CRP; on the third and fifth postoperative days, respectively, the areas under the curve were 0.87 and 0.94. These results imply that, in contrast to previously established biochemical markers like CRP and WBC, PCT may function as an earlier, more sensitive, and more trustworthy indicator of anastomotic leak [10]

Similar to this, the study "Biomarkers and anastomotic leakage in colorectal surgery: C-reactive protein trajectory is the gold standard evaluated the efficacy of gamma-glutamyl transferase, PCT, WBC, and CRP as predictive indicators for anastomotic leakage after colorectal surgery. For CRP, PCT, and WBC, the data showed a correlation between the biomarker trajectory and anastomotic leakage. Based on trajectory, however, CRP was found to be the better biomarker, with an area under the receiver operator curve of 0.961. These results demonstrate the possibility of CRP trajectory as a highly precise diagnostic tool for determining the presence of anastomotic leakage that needs to be addressed [11].

Additionally, to assess the diagnostic accuracy of postoperative CRP and PCT for anastomotic leak, a systematic review and meta-analysis titled "C-reactive Protein and Procalcitonin Levels to Predict Anastomotic Leak After Colorectal Surgery synthesized data from 25 studies involving 11,144 patients. The results of the investigation showed that individuals at low risk of developing anastomotic leak may be identified by using CRP and PCT serum values lower than established cut-

offs on postoperative days 3 to 5 [12].

A significant side effect that can arise after colon surgery is an anastomotic leak. This is especially true for surgeries involving gastrointestinal anastomosis, which is the surgical joining of two segments of the colon. This consequence is the intestinal contents leaking from the surgical anastomosis site, which can cause sepsis, peritonitis, and other potentially fatal diseases. Anastomotic leaks must be identified and treated promptly in order to improve patient outcomes and prognosis. Thus, it is critical for clinical practice to find biomarkers or clinical signs linked to a higher risk of anastomotic leak.

The paper titled "Updates of Risk Factors for Anastomotic Leakage after Colorectal Surgery lists a number of risk factors for anastomotic leakage and divides them into factors have been linked to modifiable risk factors, including alcohol and smoke use, obesity, preoperative irradiation, and the use of steroids or nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medicines. Furthermore, perioperative blood transfusion has been found to be a significant anastomotic failure risk factor. These results highlight how crucial it is to address modifiable risk factors in order to reduce the possibility of anastomotic leakage in the preoperative phase [13].

Comparably, the goal of the study "Different Risk Factors for Early and Late Colorectal Anastomotic Leakage in a Nationwide Audit was to evaluate how risk factors for early and late anastomotic leakage differed from one another. The results of the study showed that late anastomotic leakage was more strongly correlated with patient-related factors like comorbidities, preoperative tumor complications, and preoperative radiation, whereas early anastomotic leakage was primarily associated with surgery-related factors like BMI, laparoscopy, emergency surgery, and the absence of diverting ileostomy. These findings suggest that the etiology of anastomotic leakage may vary depending on the timing of occurrence, with early leakage often attributable to technical failures during surgery and late leakage associated with healing deficiencies and patient frailty [14].

Additionally, BMI greater than 30 kg/m² and "after-hours" anastomosis creation were found to be independent risk factors for colorectal anastomotic leakage in the study "After-hours colorectal surgery: a risk factor for anastomotic leakage. This study highlights how crucial it is to take into account perioperative variables, such as the surgical date, when forecasting the likelihood of anastomotic leaking [15].

The results present study provides, important information about how age affects anastomotic leak prognosis. Increased risk of anastomotic leaks and other postoperative problems can result from

physiological changes brought on by aging, such as decreased immune function, impaired wound healing, and decreased tissue suppleness. By elucidating age-specific patterns in leak detection rates, clinicians can better anticipate and manage the challenges associated with surgical interventions in older patient populations.

According to the study's findings, PCT and CRP levels may be useful predictive biomarkers for anastomotic leak, allowing medical professionals to classify patients according to their risk profile and modify their treatment plans accordingly. To reduce the risk of leak-related problems, individuals with elevated CRP and PCT levels, for instance, can benefit from closer monitoring, early imaging investigations, or even preventive surgical surgery.

Studies assessing biomarkers from urine, mediastinal microdialysis, peritoneal and mediastinal drains, and systemic circulation were included in the evaluation. Current biomarkers were considered poor predictors of AL due to insufficient sensitivity and positive predictive value, while biomarkers including leukocytes and C-reactive protein (CRP) showed promise in eliminating AL due to their high specificity and negative predictive values. This emphasizes the necessity for more investigation to find more effective diagnostic instruments for AL prediction in this patient group [16].

These findings highlight the potential of biomarkers, particularly CRP and MMP9, in facilitating early detection and risk assessment of AL in patients undergoing bowel surgery through the incorporation of biomarker analysis into standard clinical procedures, medical professionals could become more proficient in identifying patients who are at an elevated risk of AL and executing prompt interventions to alleviate this grave consequence. However, to prove their widespread application in clinical settings, more validation research and assay standardization are required for biomarkers. Additionally, biomarker-based prediction models should be interpreted in conjunction with clinical parameters to optimize their diagnostic accuracy and clinical utility.

Conclusions

The present study concluded that the anastomotic leak which pose serious threats to the life of the patient and put extra financial burden thereof. However apart from analysing factors for prevention of anastomotic leak, early suspicion of it also carries a lot of importance. Because early intervention specifically within first 10 days can very well minimise the detrimental impact of this ghastly postoperative condition. However, because clinical symptoms are often ambiguous and there are not many trustworthy biomarkers for early

identification, leak diagnosis is difficult. Hence there is always a room for use of biomarkers for early detection of anastomotic leak. Ultimately, the integration of biomarker monitoring into routine postoperative care protocols has the potential to revolutionize patient care and improve outcomes following bowel surgery.

References

- Hyman N, Manchester TL, Osler T, Burns B, Cataldo PA. Anastomotic leaks after intestinal anastomosis: it's later than you think. *Ann Surg.* 2007 Feb;245(2):254-8. doi: 10.1097/01.sla.0000225083.27182.85. PMID: 17245179; PMCID: PMC1876987.
- Hernandez PT, Paspulati RM, Shanmugan S. Diagnosis of Anastomotic Leak. *Clin Colon Rectal Surg.* 2021 Nov 23;34(6):391-399. doi: 10.1055/s-0041-1735270. PMID: 34853560; PMCID: PMC8610633.
- Gray M, Marland JRK, Murray AF, Argyle DJ, Potter MA. Predictive and Diagnostic Biomarkers of Anastomotic Leakage: A Precision Medicine Approach for Colorectal Cancer Patients. *J Pers Med.* 2021 May 25;11(6):471. s.l. : doi: 10.3390/jpm11060471. PMID: 34070 59 3; PMCID: PMC8229046.
- Samsudin I, Vasikaran SD. Clinical Utility and Measurement of Procalcitonin. *Clin Biochem Rev.* 2017 Apr;38(2):59-68. PMID: 29332972; PMCID: PMC5759088.
- Lee H. Procalcitonin as a biomarker of infectious diseases. *Korean J Intern Med.* 2013 May;28(3):285-91. doi: 10.3904/kjim.2013.28.3.285. Epub 2013 May 1. PMID: 23682219; PMCID: PMC3654123.
- Garcia-Granero, Alvaro & Frasson, Matteo & flor-lorente, Blas & Blanco Antona, Francisco & Puga, Ramon & Carratalá, Arturo & Garcia-Granero, Eduardo. (2013). Procalcitonin and C-Reactive Protein as . s.l. : Early Predictors of Anastomotic Leak in Colorectal Surgery: A Prospective Observational Study. *Diseases of the colon and rectum.* 56. 475-83. 10.1097/DCR.0b013e31826ce825.
- Lagoutte N, Facy O, Ravoire A, Chalumeau C, Jonval L, Rat P, Ortega-Deballon P. C-reactive protein and procalcitonin for the early detection of anastomotic leakage after elective colorectal surgery: pilot study in 100 patients. . s.l. : *Journal of visceral surgery.* 2012 Oct 1;149(5):e345-9.
- Garcia-Granero A, Frasson M, Flor-Lorente B, Blanco F, Puga R, Carratalá A, Garcia-Granero E. Procalcitonin and C-reactive protein as early predictors of anastomotic leak in colorectal surgery: a prospective observational study. . s.l. : *Diseases of the colon & rectum.* 2013 Apr 1;56(4):475-83.
- Lindberg M, Åsberg A, Myrvold HE, Hole A, Rydning A, Bjerve KS. Reference intervals for procalcitonin and C-reactive protein after major abdominal surgery. *Scandinavian journal of clinical and laboratory investigation.* 2002 Jan 1;62(3):189-94.
- Giaccaglia V, Salvi PF, Cunsolo GV, Sparagna A, Antonelli MS, Nigri G, Balducci G, Ziparo V. Procalcitonin, as an early biomarker of colorectal anastomotic leak, facilitates enhanced recovery after surgery. *Journal of critical care.* 2014 Aug 1;29(4):528-3.
- Smith SR, Pockney P, Holmes R, Doig F, Attia J, Holliday E, Carroll R, Draganic B. Biomarkers and anastomotic leakage in colorectal surgery: C-reactive protein trajectory is the gold standard. *ANZ journal of surgery.* 2018 May;88(5):440-4.
- Bona D, Danelli P, Sozzi A, Sanzi M, Cayre L, Lombardo F, Bonitta G, Cavalli M, Campanelli G, Aiolfi A. C-reactive protein and procalcitonin levels to Predict Anastomotic Leak after colorectal surgery: systematic review and Meta-analysis. . s.l. : *Journal of Gastrointestinal Surgery.* 2023 Jan 1;27(1):166-79.
- Zarnescu EC, Zarnescu NO, Costea R. Updates of risk factors for anastomotic leakage after colorectal surgery. *Diagnostics.* 2021 Dec 17;11(12):2382.
- Sparreboom CL, van Groningen JT, Lingsma HF, Wouters MW, Menon AG, Kleinrensink GJ, Jeekel J, Lange JF, Dutch ColoRectal Audit group. Different risk factors for early and late colorectal anastomotic leakage in a nationwide audit. . s.l. : *Diseases of the Colon & Rectum.* 2018 Nov 1;61(11):1258-66.
- Komen N, Dijk JW, Lalmahomed Z, Klop K, Hop W, Kleinrensink GJ, Jeekel H, Ruud Schouten W, Lange JF. After-hours colorectal surgery: a risk factor for anastomotic leakage. *International journal of colorectal disease.* 2009 Jul;24:789-95.
- de Mooij CM, Maassen van den Brink M, Merry A, Tweed T, Stoot J. Systematic review of the role of biomarkers in predicting anastomotic leakage following gastroesophageal cancer surgery. *Journal of Clinical Medicine.* 2019 Nov 17;8(11):2005.